

Role of ICT skills of University Faculty in Informatization of Society through Openness Movement in Higher Education

Manjunath kamath¹, Dr.Anil kumar²

¹Research Scholar, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

ORCID: 0000-0001-9474-6767 E-mail: vrind005@gmail.com

²Registrar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India
E-mail: akgnairs@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to emphasise the relevance and importance of Information and Communication Technology(ICT) skills of University Faculty community/people in educational institutions/universities, and how they can matter in complete change/transition in the Teaching/Learning process(Learning 3.0) and help Faculty in informatization of students(society) through Openness movement in Higher Education. This paper is of Review Type and is based on findings or secondary data gathered from case studies, journals, reputed magazines, and the internet for its preparation. ICT and web 2.0 has immensely contributed to changing the education scenario from obsolete and boring classroom learning to an innovative teaching /learning process.

ICT Skill is a topic too vast for academics to consider researching on. Anything and everything related to Computers and the Internet is the result of some sort of ICT skill usage by some individual. Heavy cost of ICT infrastructure is also a limiting factor. All the findings or issues discussed in this paper are collected from reputed journal data, reputed magazines, report from reputed and authorized institutions and reputed websites that is accepted worldwide.

Keywords: Skill, Higher Education, ICT, Web 2.0, Informatization, Openness.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Allround Development has been man's dream ever since he began civilised life. Rapid urbanisation, Growing congestion, and sustainability are pushing man to limits in terms of skill supply/demand and skill development in India as well as the world. Skill is defined as the ability to use one's knowledge effectively and readily in execution or performance. Skilling is a life-long process not limited to training institutes or the education sector.Learning is the process of linking, expanding, and improving data, information, knowledge and wisdom[5]. Man continuously learns new skills as age progresses and evolves into better humans. However, in a real-world / market-oriented world, skilling is a process through some trainers or resource persons. Skill is an activity inherent or learned from others that makes people's life easy. Examples of skills are typing, programming, running, batting, story writing and teaching skills.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- (1) To investigate how Web 3.0, ubiquitous connected artificial intelligence driven smart devices can help in higher education scenarios through ICT mechanisms.
- (2) To investigate the Role of ICT skills of the faculty in digital delivery of knowledge.
- (3) To Find out the possibility of On the job Higher Education(Learning 3.0) and proposing framework/Universities for Honourary degrees,Honourary post graduation degrees and Honourary doctorate degrees from regular or Digital Universities.

3. METHODOLOGY:

All the Findings are derived from observations either from the information available in journals, research articles, reputed magazines, websites, or Forums.

4. LITERATURE SURVEY

Table 1 given below gives a proper idea about the topic of research and its origin.

Table 1 review of related work.

S No	Year	Reference	Methodology	Findings	Gaps
1.	2007	Arbo, P. , P. Benneworth[1]	Connectivism approach.	Higher education as a binding force in a region between different professionals,Government machinery,can act as knowledge centres for social,economical and cultural development of a region first,nation second and globally last.	Does not talk about religious scriptures and true knowledge hidden in them.

2.	2018	Jasemi, M., Piri, M[2]	Literature Survey method	Paper also touches upon non-existence of globally accepted forms of knowledge or definition. This paper talks about the knowledge/Knowledge database that must be maintained in all organisations specifically in industries in any of 3 forms publication,theses, patent depending on nature of organisations.	No mention of the origin of knowledge.
3.	2021	Yuliya Shtaltovna Christina Muzzu[3]	Literature review method	<p>This paper puts light on problems faced by Resource people around the world in the post Covid-era where solutions can be found in Emergency E-Learning tools or skills using 6 important aspects/areas.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital tech use. 2. Digital resources sourcing,creating, sharing. 3. Teaching and learning. 4. Digital learning assessment. 5. Empowering learners through 	The Paper doesn't talk about cognitive skills.

				engagement. 6.Enabling learners' digital capability.	
4.	2018	T Wrahatnolo , Munoto[4]	citations /Reference method.	21st-century skills are grouped into three types, namely (1) life and career skills, (2) learning and innovation skills, and (3) media skills and information skills(Digital literacy)	Numeric data or statistics unavailable.
5.	2000	Paul E. Bierly III Eric H. Kessler Edward W.Christensen [5]	Citations/reference method.	To improve understanding of the impact of organisational learning and knowledge on competitive advantage, paper proposes a framework that includes the constructs of data, information, knowledge, and wisdom.	No diagrammatic representation or linking of components.
6.	2012	M I Jawid Nazir, Aftab Haider Rizvi, Ramachandra V Pujeri[6]	Questionnaire and sampling method	After the study of the area and carrying out experiments a model is proposed saying Ease of Learning(EOL), Ease of Understanding(EOU),Amended Attentiveness(AA), Increased	Smaller and less number of university students taken as respondents.Hence has geographical limitations.

				Interaction(II), Convenience(C) which can be controlled using multimedia in Teaching/Learning process have a significant effect on skill development process.	
7.	2014	Eugenia Smyrnova-Trybulska, Piet Kommers, Margriet Simmerling[7]	Literature review on blended learning(E-learning) and its advantages.	<p>1. Explanation of competence, skill and learning.</p> <p>2. Reason for choosing distance education over other modes.</p> <p>3. Supports digital learning without support of data.</p>	No mathematical proof in above literature. It would have been great if author had put some data to support her views or arguments.
8.	1998	Davenport, T. Prusak, L.[8]	Literature survey on organisational knowledge	<p>1. Definition of organisational knowledge.</p> <p>2. Different types of knowledge.</p>	No statistics, diagrams showing different forms of knowledge and their relationship.
9.	1998	M Gibbons[9]	Literature survey on different modes of higher education and relevance.	Changing dynamics of relevance of higher education, social responsibility, partnerships and alliances leading to competitions and collaborations.	Too little content on mode 2 and virtual universities.
10.	2016	G Vijayudu[10]	Literature Survey of Higher Education.	Challenges or problems facing Higher education, stress on Value based Education, Government	No diagrammatic model representations .

				schemes like RUSA, PMEGP, RGUMY.Skill development missions.	
11.	2003	Heather Bircham.[11]	Theoretical framework.	The kind of question structure has an effect on knowledge outcome or sharing by the recipient of the question.	No supporting numeric data.
12.	2017	Wolhunter.[12]	Literature review	The paper talk about different forces/factors influencing Education policy. Detailed explanation of past, present and future of Education scenarios. Challenges coming.	No statistics on Education or diagrammatic representations .
13.	2012	Husain, F. [13]	Imagination/Cognition method.	Mention of web 3.0 and some of the prototype e-learning 3.0 management systems.	No clear cut idea/model about web 3.0 and E-Learning 3.0.

The skill of any working professional can be classified as Generic skills and Technical skills (Domain skills) [14] and this applies to all professional fields including teaching. And Teachers/Faculty need to have 12 Generic Skills to do efficient teaching. They are

- i. Oral Communication[15]
- ii. Written Communication[15]
- iii. Problem Solving[15]
- iv. Analysis[15]
- v. Information and Communication Technology(ICT)[15]
- vi. Critical Evaluation[15]
- vii. Team Work[15]
- viii. Employability and Further study[15]
- ix. Independent Lifelong Learning[15]

- x. Leadership and Decision-making[15]
- xi. Ethical Standards[15]
- xii. Responsibility and Accountability[15].

Numerous definitions have been proposed for information and communication technology, it can be said that information and communication technology according to [16] is defined as

- Includes issues related to science, advanced topics and computer technology, computer design, implementation of information systems, and its applications[16].
- Is a combination of traditional knowledge of computer and communications technology to store, process, and transfer any data (including text, audio, image, video) [16].

Education is process of facilitating learning in other words acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, morals, beliefs, habits and personal development[17]. Education started as the transmission of cultural heritage from one generation to next. New age Education goals include liberation of learners, critical thinking about provided information, skills (vocational and general) needed for modern society[17]. Basically, there are 3 types of Education. Formal Education, Informal Education, and Non-formal Education are these types. Formal Education is a process where a student or learner goes to some institute for learning and a Faculty or resource person is delivering some information to be grasped by learners. In active learning, both students and Faculty get some knowledge whereas in passive learning only one person gets knowledge. Informal Education is obtained outside the academic framework most probably from parents, print-audio-video media, or websites. Non-formal Education is temporary courses that one attends to get some additional skills for getting jobs or doing business.

[18] Defines “Informatization of education is a set of interrelated organisational and legal, socio-economic, educational, methodological, scientific-technical, industrial and management processes. These processes are aimed at providing information, computing, and telecommunication needs (other needs related to the implementation of methods and tools of information and communication technologies — ICT) of participants of the educational process, as well as those who manage and maintain this process (including those who provide its scientific and methodological support and development)”.

[18] Also discusses “Primary goals of informatization of education we have to include the following components as:

- establishment of skills of self-education and self-realisation;
- advancement of the potential of each person, thereby development of intellectual potential of the nation;
- development of the educational spectrum of services for people with special needs;
- rise in the quality of training or Higher education for it provides favourable conditions;
- creation of new pedagogical tools ;
- increasing the aptitude to analyse the extended knowledge and skills of students;
- establishment of the society with the informatively experienced population ; ”.

Informatization of education is regarded as an area of pedagogical science, which creates a certain type of integrity, providing the educational sector with the methodology, theory and practice to perfect and optimise the use of ICT tools in comfortable and health-saving conditions[19].

[20] Explains the factors that influence the development of the modern stage of informatization of education.

1. Globalisation of information interaction in synchronous and asynchronous modes.
2. Pedagogical technologies and information and communication technologies merge to become same and help one another to penetrate into the masses or population.
3. Conflict of Individual reality versus virtual reality driving physical, social and mental aspects of individual and world around him.
4. Network information dependence of the individual on:
 - Information interaction with anonymous partners, both real and virtual;
 - Use of information-loaded, eye-catching, old fashioned information resources;
 - Forceful promotion in the process of virtual management of objects and events;
 - Uncontrolled production of fake information.
5. Individual suffering from the condition called as “mental infantilism” for losing individual motivation for ones’ presence in the real world and distancing from communication with people which entails greater danger to the mental health of the person.

The Table 2 below gives the shift in the role of Faculties in the past and present context of Education:

Changes in Teachers' Roles		
	From	To
1.	The transmitter of Knowledge	Guide & Facilitator of Knowledge[21]
2.	Controller of Learning	Creator of Learning Environment[21]
3.	Always Expert	Collaborator & Co-learner[21]
4.	Learning to use ICT	Using ICT to Enhance Learning[21]
5.	Didactive/Expository	Interactive/Experiential/Explorator[21]

ICT skills in relation to Modern day university Faculty’s role

1. ICT skills of the University Faculty can help him to achieve the role of Guide and Facilitator of Knowledge by sharing journal articles and other resources such as PowerPoint presentations, Annual study reports, and e-books by well-recognized authors and institutions like ILO, UNESCO, NASSCOM, MHRD, MICROSOFT.

2. Creation of the Learning Environment by the Faculty community is influenced by Andragogical and technological factors. Andragogical methods are in Faculty's control, that is how he/she wants to deliver the lecture or share information, make learning interesting, and use advanced information technologies or software available right now. Technological factors like connectivity issues, satellite failures, protocol mismatch, hardware issues, and copyright issues, can influence the interaction between Faculty and a Student.

3. Collaborator and Co-learner is the new Role given to Faculty as Collaborator and Co-learner would make students at ease with the Faculty. The new role would make the entire environment relaxed and facilitate greater interactions among students and Faculty. Free and Open interactions would encourage students to ask questions regarding subjects or personal matters. Faculty would also be involved in investigating solutions to current problems along with the students. Hence there is learning happening in students as well as Faculties. Hence we can say students and Faculty as learners and better learners.

4. Using ICT to enhance Learning can be done using Newer Apps and Tools like Google form for conducting tests and getting survey data, Cisco Webex and Google meet for conducting online classes, Smart Boards for Attractive Presentations, Google Drive for storing data/information permanently, Google platform for almost any work.

5. Faculty today has to be Fully interactive hence if he is "actively" using technologies (ICT) like Google Meet or Cisco Webex and Whatsapp Messengers that means Faculty is sufficiently interactive and responding to student concerns. ICT technologies would make a Faculty to be Fully explorer of knowledge and Wisdom seeking as most of the search technologies like Google scholar are linked to knowledge sources.

All the above is happening online because of the wonder called "Web 2.0"

The term "Web 2.0" is commonly associated with web applications that facilitate interactive information sharing, interoperability, user-centred design, and collaboration on the World Wide Web[22]. A "Web 2.0" site allows its users to interact with other users or to change website content, in contrast to non-interactive websites where users are limited to the passive viewing of information that is provided to them[22].

Characteristics of web 2.0:

- i. Collaboration.
- ii. Openness.
- iii. Modularity.
- iv. User Control.
- v. Identity.
- vi. Evolving Content [22].

The characteristics listed above help us to solve the education-related problem in the following ways:

1. The collaboration feature of web 2.0 "helps Faculty to create, collaborate, edit, categorise, exchange, and promote. Some of the best available collaboration tools like 1. Social Networks 2. Blogs 3. Micro Blogging 4. RSS and Aggregators 5. Video-Sharing 6. Photo Sharing 7. Wiki 8. Podcast 9. Bookmarks 10. Virtual World 11. Content Rating, helps faculty to share, create and learn".

2. The openness of web 2.0 is the concept that emerges with the 'open science' or 'wiki science' or 'Science 2.0' theory that nobody owns knowledge or content and anyone can modify anything - from programming code, journal articles, songs, video[23]. So openness can be further applied to different aspects like

- Openness to ‘experience’[23]
 - Openness to criticism[23]
 - Openness to interpretation[23]
 - Openness to the Other[23]
 - Open science communications technologies[23]
 - Openness=freedom[23]
 - Open science governance[23].
3. The modularity feature of Web 2.0 is contradiction to monolithic(composed all in one piece). Users are able to pick and choose from a set of interoperating components in order to build something that meets their needs[24].
 4. In user control characteristics, the user can exercise what he wants to see and how he wants to see it. The user is the ultimate authority for controlling the content and mode of transmission. Once Faculty becomes the admin of Web 2.0 Tools he can control other users’ participation levels and track and bolster the speed of work of students by sending automated or timer set commands to targeted Students.
 5. The user’s Identity can be increasingly manipulated or changed according to the User’s wish to suit the scenario. Hence Faculty sometimes may not be interested in revealing their identity to a student in order to check up on the activities of students so they can change the profile names whenever he or she wishes to hide from the students and come back to real profile names whenever he wants them to know his real name.
 6. Evolving content is another reason why web 2.0 has been this popular. A dynamic and newer addition to kinds of content ranging from static text to live video streaming has made Web content nowadays a mesmerizing experience. The entire Universe is accessible at the click of a button.

Owing to these characteristics of Web 2.0 and the Internet platforms, ICT tools have empowered Faculty to efficiently manage and coordinate the online classroom for teaching or learning environment.

“Connectionism” is a new term used now, since every device is probably connected to the Internet and using Information technology solutions we can use solutions developed in some cities say San Francisco(USA) to solve problems in the classroom environment in Mangalore(India)[18].

Contextual learning means drawing inspiration from the outside world and applying real-world strategies and methods to academic problems[25].

Educational Fundamentalism should be totally disapproved of in all kinds of learning. Educational Fundamentalism is always preaching one side of the story or approach or ideology or thinking[26].

Information service of education allows actors of the system to collect and store data of various components in the education process that is happening in the education scenario and disseminate it to the public[26].

Novelty, dynamism, and diversity are the key properties of information, which directly affect the content, methods, and forms of education[27].

In the modern theory of education, it is necessary to integrate the ideas of several didactic paradigms: Behaviourism→Cognitivism→Constructivism→Connectivism[28]. Behaviourism is more on behaviour or method of learning than the content of learning. Cognitivism means more on scientific facts and reasoning than on methods and finding connections between existing knowledge.

Constructivism is a phenomenon where learners take away facts and information and construct new knowledge or information. Connectivism is the art of connecting old knowledge with newer information and knowledge. So the network is built using this connection that forms a network of logic with brain activity as a central concept. Learning can also be classified as Cognitive, Affective and Psychomotor skills. Affective learning skills are those skills which are guided by beliefs, attitudes, interests and motivation and values which require a valuation or response of different things according to individual interests and beliefs. Psychomotor learning is demonstrated by physical skills such as movement, speed, and strength which require entire body and mind co-ordination[29].

5. CURRENT STATUS OF THE SYSTEM: Currently the system is inflexible where management and Faculties are having all the say in various aspects of Education like Educational resources used in the course, syllabus formulation, curricula formation, and conduct of the Assessment process.

6. ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH GAPS:

Higher Education should be open to up-gradation and must be given the flexibility to change as Technology changes rapidly.' Openness in Higher Education is the sum of all aspects like Openness in the syllabus, openness in the curriculum, openness in Assessment, and openness in the Technological and Educational resources. Openness is an anti-ownership and anti-profiteering concept. Openness is brought about by accepting and approving contributions from all kinds of people in society. Openness in Education can easily be brought about by the technological mass connectivity, change in management attitude, and efforts of the people in the society. People in the society mean policymakers, all citizens of the country/state/city, and visiting tourists of a place or nation.

As more and more people are connected through smart devices,5G arrival in the world, cost of Higher education increasing tremendously and mobility for research work/Learning/Work would happen, this would make people unavailable at one location to carry their education forward. So there needs an efforts in opening the system which now in india is closed in most education institutions, hence initially or near future we would see digital universities mushrooming in the country. After that big sci-tech companies would step-in and enter the market then we would have Google University, L&T University, Toyota University, several other domain specific universities to impart job ready skills for growing population. In the long term scenario, learning 3.0 and open movement in higher education would pick up pace and eventually we would have on-the job Education becoming the norm and these Government/Government authorised big sci-tech companies giving either giving skill certificates or skill degrees certificates for their learning outcomes. So there is Research Gap that is existing in current Literature are:

- i. Research Gap 1:To connect all the next generation technologies like AI, Machine learning, Robotics, Smart Devices which is Ubiquitous computing and use it and combined power of Web 3.0,5G for learning using ICT mechanism.
- ii. Research Gap 2:To Formulate plan for Digital University and Learning 3.0(Any-where,Any-How,Any-Time,Any-Body,Any-Means Learning).
- iii. Research Gap 3:To Find out possibility of alternate Degree (On-the-job Degree/Learning 3.x) programmes by working in reputed or international or Government certified institutions.

7.RESEARCH AGENDA:

1. How smart devices would connect to give us a fully connected world using 5G/Web 3.0 Framework/ubiquitous computing?
2. How different aspects of life would be fully online/digitized including Universities and Learning Institutions to improve ease of living there by helping in ease of learning?
3. How can learning 3.0 be implemented to impart true knowledge?
4. How knowledge created during working in an organization would help the knowledge database (reputed journals),Wikipedia or Google scholar of the world ?

8. FINAL RESEARCH TOPIC:

Based on research gaps, current findings and keywords related to education field and openness to achieve maximum coverage, an alternative or new framework can be proposed to set up learning 3.0 universities which make students do work in companies or institutions then assess them based on their performance in various chores assigned to them in those offices or organisations.

9.LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH :

Limitation of the proposal is that Government or Existent Government Universities has to first provide Technical support for these companies in giving degrees or topics for learning/working/Researching. If Government or Existing Government Universities do not monitor these companies, these entities would indulge in malpractices or do unfair business with learners creating a confusion in the mechanism. So Government should strictly keep an eye on quality of work that is done by learners before giving degrees.

10.SUGGESTIONS FOR THE RESEARCH

Since most of the components of the Framework (5G/web3.0/Learning 3.0) is not available in the market so research is would be an effort in proposing an future ready Framework for Universities that would solve most of the problems existing in current University framework.

11. CONCLUSION:

Long and strenuous exercise of classroom teaching has been replaced by powerful ICT tools which make the teaching jobs easier and more interesting. Different scenarios may require the usage of different tools. Whatever the tool is, the idea is to make the learning environment more interactive and engaging. Thus ICT usage can transform the traditional knowledge delivery classroom into a knowledge creation structure by student-Faculty engagement .Once the entire population is connected, we would have digital universities in the near future where students need not go to campus daily and but can do work in regular hours and do degrees in these universities at his convenience. Long term prediction is that because of governments push to up-skill the entire population we would have sci-tech innovation cum services/product universities would support the initiative for it sees good opportunity to make good money.

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